

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT FLOODING METHODS USED FOR RICE CULTIVATION AT THE STATE RICE FARM “BOSHOD”.

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Abstract: *A field experiment was carried out at the State Rice Farm of Boshod in the Chimkent Region, the Republic of Kazakhstan, to compare and contrast the effects of four flooding methods on the production of the rice variety “Uros-59”. The flooding methods included: deep flooding (20cm) – A₀; shallow flooding (10-15cm) - A₁; initial shallow flooding (10-15cm) with intermittent renewal of water -A₂ and moistening the soil up to the tillering phase of the rice before flooding (15cm) -A₃. The percent germination, biometric measurements, leaf surface area and yield levels of the rice plants grown under the different variants of flooding were taken; and the economic rentability of the different flooding methods for the rice production calculated. The deep flooding method-(A₀) showed the lowest (70%) seed germination rate. Generally, the variant A₃ exhibited outstanding results with the highest percentage of seed germination (90 %) and comparatively good physiological growth of the rice variety “Uros-59. With the A₃ variant the quantity of irrigation water used was about 2000 m³/Ha lower than the control (A₀). Variant A₃ also registered relatively the highest yields (68.5centiner/Ha) and the most rentable method of irrigation (100 %). The variant A₃ was, therefore, recommended for the State Rice Farm at Boshod.*

Keywords: Intermittent, Germination, Biometric, Variants, Rentability

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the problem

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) from the family Graminea, is one of the indigenous crops and staple food used by about two-thirds (2/3) of the human population (Jones, 1995). It grows 1-1.8 m tall; has long slender leaves (20-100 cm) which are 2-2.5 cm broad, and with inflorescence of 30-50 cm long. Its tillers or culms produce terminal panicles (loosed or compacted depending on variety). These contain many spikelets (56-520) which produce about 90-150 seeds (Atwell et. al., 1982). The plant is mainly self-pollinated, but up to 3% cross-pollination can occur. It is intended for an area with low labor cost and high

rainfall as it is capital-intensive to cultivate. Traditional method of cultivation is by flooding the fields while, or after setting the young seedlings. While flooding is not mandatory for the cultivation, all other cultivation methods require high efforts in weed and pest control during the growing period (International Rice Research Institutes, 2009).

Compared with other crops, rice can give high economic returns using less-productive and poor lands (alkaline soils) for cultivation, provided water is not a limiting factor and this is even more effective when a rotation with legumes is practiced. Studies by Black (2010) show that rice yield has fallen by 10-20% as a result of rising

temperatures and decreasing solar radiations during the later years of the 20th century. Reasons for this could include increased respiration, increasing atmospheric CO₂ during the warm night which expends the energy which makes it difficult for rice to photosynthesize. Reports from BBC News (2010) and Peng *et al.* (2009) also revealed that rice yield is falling due to global warming.

1.2. Problem Statement

It is generally known from literature that flooding methods give better returns than non-flooding ones as far as rice production is concerned (Clermont-Dauphin, 2010). A field experiment was, therefore, carried out to investigate the type of flooding method that will give better returns on the production of rice variety Uros-59 at the State Rice Farm ‘Boshod’.

1.3. Justification

All rice types and varieties are typically hydrophytes and thus give the greatest yield only under conditions of flooding, and early constant flooding suppresses weed growth and reduces weeding cost (Ishmael *et al.*, 2012). Angaji *et al.* (2010) also reported that rice only needs a high moistened soil (up to saturation levels) without any water layer on the soil surface. This method, suites rice physiological processes better than the constant flooding. It also promotes an increase in the germination energy of the seed by 7 to 15% and an increase in plant density by 7 to 11%, as compared to constant flooding (Angaji *et al.* 2010).

Testing of different methods of flooding for rice production at ‘Boshod’ under the same prevailing local conditions provides the best basis for a sound choice or modification of an already existing irrigation method for the crop.

1.4. Aims and objectives

The aim of the study was to determine flooding methods that best enhance the production of the rice variety ‘Uros-59’ and yield good economic returns at ‘Boshod’.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The State Rice Farm Boshod is situated in a dry climatic zone (a semi-desert) with low and unevenly distributed amounts of rainfall, totaling 224.3 mm/year. The area has a meadow-grey-soil ranging from light to heavy soils, with high salinity. Absolute maximum temperature ranges from 17.6 to 42.2 °C and minimum temperature from -29.5 to 12°C. About 170 - 190 days have temperatures above 10°C in a year. Water source for irrigation is the river Sri-Dari, which has high doses of dissolved minerals of about 500-950 mg/L. Melted ice is also an important source of water for irrigation. The vegetation is grassland; mostly with short grasses, thorny shrubs and isolated trees. The nitrogen content in the soil is low, the phosphorus content is moderate, but the potassium content is high (301-400 exchangeable potassium in mg/kg soil). Predominate activities at ‘Boshod’ are crop production and animal husbandry (State Farm Boshod, 1991).

For flooding purposes the fields are made into plots of 2 to 4 hectares and dyked to hold the water in place. The surfaces of the plots are thoroughly leveled to ensure uniform flooding and sowing depths. Three main canals connect the plots with the irrigational system: the main canals (master canal), which gets water to the field from the water source; the canals from one plot to another, through some openings at the plots’ banks; the canal from the plots to water-collectors, which drains off water from the plots.

2.1 System of Fertilizer Application in the Rice Rotational System at ‘Boshod’

The rice occupies 57.2 % of the total area under crop cultivation on the State Farm ‘Boshod’. The main preceding crops to rice is alfalfa, barley, wheat, maize (for hay) and cow-pea. However, plots also allowed to fallow.

A seven-plot rice rotational system is commonly used (Table 1).

Fertilizer application is necessary for the rice or for any of the preceding-crops in the rice-rotational system. The quantity of fertilizer used for the rice production is greater than that used

Table 1: System of fertiliser application in a seven year rice rotational system in the State farm Boshod

Order of crops on plot	Main fertiliser application	Top dressing	Total fertiliser (centre per Ha.) in physical weight				
			N ₂	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Sulphate of ammonia	Super phosphate
Alfalfa 1st year	N ₄₀ P ₉₀ K		40	90	-	2.0	4.7
Alfalfa 2nd year	-	N ₄₀ P ₉₀ K	40	90	-	2.0	4.7
Rice 1st year	N ₉₀ P ₁₂₀ K	N ₄₀ PK	130	120	-	6.5	6.3
Rice 2nd year	N ₁₂₀ P ₁₂₀ K	N ₄₀ PK	160	120	-	8.0	6.3
Fallow	N ₉₀ P ₉₀ K	N ₃₀ PK	120	90	-	6.0	4.7
Rice 1st year	N ₁₀₀ P ₁₂₀ K	N ₅₀ PK	150	120	-	7.5	6.3
Rice 2nd year	N ₁₂₀ P ₁₂₀ K	N ₆₀ PK	180	120	-	9.0	6.3

Sulphate of ammonia – 20% N₂ active substance; Super - phosphate (granular) – 19% P active substance. (Source: Report from State Farm Boshod, 1991)

for any of the preceding crops. Also the quantity of fertilizer used for the rice production increased proportionally to the number of years or seasons the crop had been grown on the same piece of land. Sulphate of ammonia was used for top dressing. The main source of phosphorus was granules of super-phosphate.

As the soil had high levels of potassium (Table 1), potassium-fertilizers were not applied.

Four variants (flooding methods) for rice production were tested:

A₀ – Constant flooding with initial water depth of 10cm as the control, In this case, the water levels (depths) at the time of sowing was 10 cm; after sprouting the water level was raised to 15 cm to suppress weeds. At the rice tillering phase, the water level was decreased to 5 cm to allow cultural practices to be effected. A week after this, the water level was raised to 15 cm and remained at this level up to grain maturity. Two weeks before harvesting, the water level was reduced to 0 cm to prepare the rice field for harvesting.

A₁ – Constant flooding with initial water depth of 20 cm. This varies from the control (A₀) only from the sowing to sprouting time, where the water level was 20 cm to suppress weeds.

A₂ – Constant flooding with initial water depth of 10 to 15 cm, with periodic water renewal. Two

to three times water renewal are done before the rice tillering-phase to wash off or leach out salt content in the soil. The water is then sustained at 10-15 cm levels up to maturity and drained from the checks some two weeks before harvesting.

A₃ – Initial soil moistening to saturation levels, accompanied with flooding”. The soil is moistened to 80-100 % saturation, from sowing to the rice tillering phase. From tillering-phase up to maturity, the plots are flooded to 10-15 cm depths. The field is drained two weeks before the rice is harvested.

The indigenous rice variety, “Uros-59”, was sown on fields which were occupied by a two-year alfalfa-preceding-crop.

The cultivation method was used to determine the following parameters:

Percent germination of the rice seeds; Development of the shooting and rooting systems; Irrigation dynamics and machinery were used to determine the levels of water during the vegetative phase of rice for each irrigation method.

The determination of the yield of the crop for each of the four variants was determined by weighing the harvested produce per hectare of land space for each variant.

2.2 Determination of Economic Effectiveness and the Level Rentability

The economic effectiveness was determined by measuring the mean yield and multiplying it by the price per 100kg or centner of Rubles for each variant and then subtracting the price of product as per the per the experimental data for each variant. This gave the profit obtained in Rubles on each of the use of each of the variants.

The level of rentability of each variant was determined as a ratio of the price of product as per the experimental data for each variant to the profit obtained on Rubles on each variants expressed in percentage.

The results of each of the variants were compared and contrasted to ascertain the most suitable flooding method, from which conclusions and recommendations were drawn.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prolonged and deep flooding (20 cm) in variant A₁ resulted in a high death rate of seeds (35%), as compared to 10% in variant A₃, where there was no water layer on the soil surface during the period of seed germination (Fig 1). The control variant (A₀) and variant A₂ gave intermediate results of 30% death rate.

Fig. 1: Effect of different flooding variants on the germination and death rates of rice seeds.

In general, the biometric properties of the rice plant, as shown in Fig. 3, are expressed best in variant A₃ as compared to other variants, including the control (A₀). However the quality of seeds produced was best in the control variant (A₀) with the least percent of empty seeds (7.8 %) and better 1000- seeds weight (30.5 g).

A positive correlation (R= 0.70) existed between the leaf surface area and yield. The variant A₃ gave the best results (260 cm² and 6.85 tonne / Ha), and variant A₂ the least results (21.2 cm² and 500.5 / Ha). All the variants gave relatively good results (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2: Effects of types of flooding method on germination of rice seed

Fig. 3: Effects of different flooding methods on biometric measurements for the rice variety “Urios-59”.

Fig. 4: Effects of different flooding methods on the leaf surface area (cm²) and yield for the rice variety “Urios-59”.

Fig. 5: Effects Economic effectiveness of the various flooding methods on rice cultivation.

To assess the rentability of the variants used in the investigation, the economic returns on rice production for each flooding method was calculated. The most rentable variant was A₃ (Fig. 5), the rentability being 100 % as compared to 73% for the control (A₀). The least rentable variant was variant A₂ (22.6 %).

4. CONCLUSION

The effects of four flooding methods on rice production in “Boshod” indicated that long period of flooding and deep flooding of the soil negatively affected as the germination rate of rice seeds was comparatively slow and as high as 35% of the seeds failed to germinate.

The flooding method practiced in variant A₃ enabled the rice plant to grow better physiologically and produced relatively the highest yield. The variant A₃ used relatively lower quantities of irrigation water, about 2000 m³/Ha lower than that used in the control variant (A₀). Thus, the variant A₃ is the rentable method of irrigation for rice production at “Boshod”.

Recommendations

Though the adopted flooding method of irrigation (variant A₀ – the control) produced good results, it could not match the outstanding results of variant A₃.

Any of these two variants, A₀ and A₃, could be recommended for adoption for rice production at “Boshod”. However, as water is becoming scarce in the area, the following two options could be considered:

- i. Maintain the total area for rice production and adopt the irrigation variant A₃, where relatively lesser amounts of water is needed for irrigation, or
- ii. Maintain the widely used method of irrigation (variant A₀) but reduce the size of the total area for rice production, as this method of irrigation uses relatively greater amounts of water. The decreased area for rice production could be used to increase the area for forage production, as animal husbandry is also practiced prominently in the State Rice Farm of “Boshod”; or increase the acreage for non-hydrophytic crops that require comparatively low amounts of water. Crops such as maize, wheat, or beans could be included in the rotational system on the fallowed plots. Thus, restructuring the acreage of the rotational system is necessary in this case.

Similar recommendations were made by Morteza et al. (2008) for the California area, in which surface flooding was decreased by 31% (Morteza et al., 2008).

Results of our study, therefore, suggest that irrigation methods variants A₁ and A₂ could be discarded, since they waste a lot of scarce water. Specifically, the variant A₁ could be replaced by a modification of variant A₀. With a more efficient weedicide application, couple with maintaining water on the soil surface, weeds can be efficiently controlled. The important role placed by variant A₂ – addressing salinity issues could be taken care of by increasing the efficiency of the already existing vertical drainage system on such farm lands, with variant A₀ flooding system to reduce the salinity of the soil.

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